

Altering substrate specificity of a thermostable bacterial monoamine oxidase by structure-based mutagenesis

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ABSTRACT

Bacterial monoamine oxidases (MAOs) are FAD-dependent proteins catalyzing a relevant reaction for many industrial biocatalytic applications, ranging from production of enantiomerically pure building blocks for pharmaceutical synthesis to biosensors for monitoring food and beverage quality. The thermostable MAO enzyme from *Thermoanaerobacteriales* bacterium (MAO_{Tb}) is about 36 % identical to both putrescine oxidase and human MAOs and can be efficiently produced in *Escherichia coli*. MAO_{Tb} preferentially acts on *n*-alkyl monoamines but shows detectable activity also on polyamines and aromatic monoamines. The crystal structures of MAO_{Tb} in complex with putrescine, benzylamine, spermidine and *n*-heptylamine at resolution ranging from 1.6 to 2.3 Å resolution revealed the binding mode of substrates to the enzyme. The MAO_{Tb} active site is highly conserved in the inner part of the cavity in front of the flavin ring (*re* face), where the presence of two tyrosine residues creates the substrate amine binding site that is found also in human MAOs. Instead, more distantly from the flavin, the entrance of the catalytic site is much more open in MAO_{Tb} and features a different arrangement of amino acids. Site-directed mutagenesis targeting residues Ala168, Thr199 and Val324 allowed the identification of key residues in ligand binding to alter substrate specificity. The A168D variant showed a higher activity on putrescine than wild-type, whereas by replacing either Thr199 or Val324 to Trp a marked enhancement in k_{cat}/K_M values was found on *n*-alkyl-monoamines and on aromatic amines.

1. Introduction

Monoamine oxidases (MAOs) are a family of flavin-dependent enzymes that catalyze the oxidative deamination of either primary, secondary or tertiary amine substrates, producing imines as intermediate products [1]. The imines are then non-enzymatically hydrolyzed to aldehydes, while the FAD cofactor is regenerated to its oxidized state by molecular oxygen resulting in hydrogen peroxide and ammonia formation [2]. Mammalian MAOs are integral membrane proteins anchored to the outer mitochondrial membrane through a C-terminal helix [3]. Although they are expressed in different organs of the human body, the crucial role of these enzymes is in the central nervous system where they regulate the balance of neurotransmitters and exogenous amines, hence representing validated drug targets for neurological pathologies [4]. Homologues of mammalian MAO enzymes are found also in other tetrapods and in fish, as well as in lower eukaryotes. In these latter

organisms, MAOs are not associated with mitochondria and they lack the membrane-binding domain. The *Aspergillus niger* MAO N is a soluble enzyme that was extensively investigated to tailor variants acting on amine substrates for enantioselective amine synthesis [5]. This is a relevant aspect because optically active amines can be used as building blocks of various pharmaceutically active substances and agrochemicals [6]. The usage of enzymes represents a sustainable alternative to traditional chemical synthesis, enabling highly selective oxidation reactions under mild conditions with a lower burden on the environment. In addition, MAOs can also be employed for the biodegradation of odorous pollutants derived from volatile aliphatic amines [7] and as biosensors for monitoring food and beverage quality or assessing the freshness of biological samples [8,9]. High levels of biogenic amines are toxic to human consumption and many of them may act as exogenous neuroactive molecules even at low concentrations. The detection of biogenic amines in food is often carried out through expensive and

Abbreviations: MAO, monoamine oxidase; MAO_{Tb}, monoamine oxidase from *Thermoanaerobacteriales* bacterium.

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time-consuming chromatography methods, whereas enzyme-based biosensors offer a rapid and cost-effective alternative [10].

Bacterial enzymes are suitable tools for biocatalytic applications because they are easy to be genetically manipulated and produced as recombinant proteins also on an industrial scale. They often exhibit broader substrate specificity and enhanced working stability in comparison to their eukaryotic counterparts. MAO enzymes were discovered also in bacteria where they are most likely involved in metabolizing exogenous molecules as a source of nitrogen [11]. Recently, our groups discovered a bacterial monoamine oxidase (MAO_{Tb}) from the thermophilic *Thermoanaerobacteriales* bacterium that is about 36 % identical to both putrescine oxidase and human MAOs, and can be efficiently produced in *Escherichia coli* [12]. MAO_{Tb} is highly active on *n*-alkyl monoamines and shows low but detectable activity on polyamines and aromatic monoamines. Remarkably, the enzyme is thermostable with T_m values above 60 °C in a wide range of buffer conditions and has a very good stability also in the presence of organic solvents. Taking advantage of the structural similarity of MAO_{Tb} active site to the other FAD-dependent amine oxidases, we undertook a site-directed mutagenesis approach to pinpoint key residues for ligand binding and improve activity on substrates of interest for industrial biocatalytic applications as mentioned above. This strategy was informed by structural analyses of MAO_{Tb} in complex with amine substrates (putrescine, benzylamine, spermidine and *n*-heptylamine) to outline the binding mechanism and design variants to be tested on substrates in comparison with the wild-type enzyme. Herewith, we report on the biochemical characterization of the variants A168D, A168R, T199W, V324W of MAO_{Tb}, demonstrating that targeting the T199/V324 pair leads to a marked increase in the catalytic activity on aliphatic monoamines. Although the improvement with aromatic amines is modest, it opens avenues for further enzyme engineering to develop a more effective biocatalyst.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Site-directed mutagenesis and production of recombinant MAO_{Tb} variants

Chemicals and primers to carry out mutagenesis on the MAO_{Tb} cDNA were ordered from Sigma-Aldrich (unless otherwise stated). All mutations were carried out using the QuikChange methodology (Agilent). The 25 µL PCR mix was composed of the following reagents: PfuUltra II Hotstart PCR Master Mix (12.5 µL), 1 µL of primer frw (10 µM), 1 µL of primer rev (10 µM), 1 µL of plasmid (100 ng/µL), 0.4 µL of DMSO, 0.4 µL MgCl₂ (50 µM) and MQ water up to 25 µL. For transformation, 4 µL of plasmid was added to 40 µL of *E. coli* NEB10β CaCl₂-competent cells and incubated on ice for 30 min. Cells were then heat shocked at 42 °C for 45 s and cooled down in ice for 5 min. Then, 250 µL of LB medium was added, and the cells were shaken at 300 rpm for 1 h at 37 °C; 50 µL of the recovered cells were plated on LB-agar supplemented with 50 µg mL⁻¹ ampicillin and incubated overnight at 37 °C. Plasmid isolation was performed, and mutagenesis was verified through sequencing. For overexpression of both wild-type and variants of MAO_{Tb}, a pre-inoculum of 5 mL of LB medium containing ampicillin (50 µg mL⁻¹) was grown overnight at 37 °C and used to inoculate 2 L baffled flasks containing 400 mL of TB medium supplemented with 50 µg mL⁻¹ ampicillin. Flasks were incubated at 37 °C until an OD₆₀₀ of 0.7 was reached. Expression was induced with 0.02 % L-arabinose, and cultures were left at 24 °C for 16 h before being harvested. Cells were pelleted by centrifugation (3700 rpm, 15 min, 4 °C) and stored at -20 °C.

2.2. Purification, activity assays, steady-state kinetics

Cell pellets of cultures overexpressing MAO_{Tb} proteins were resuspended into 50 mL lysis buffer (50 mM TRIS-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, pH 8.0) and cells were disrupted by sonication (5 s pulse, 7 s pause, 30 % amplitude for a total of 2 min 30 s). The supernatant was collected by

centrifuging at 11000 rpm for 50 min at 4 °C and loaded onto gravity columns containing 5 mL of Ni-Sepharose resin equilibrated with lysis buffer. The resin was incubated with the supernatant at 4 °C while rotating for 1 h. Subsequently, the column was washed with 3 column volumes of lysis buffer and 3 column volumes of wash buffer (50 mM TRIS-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, pH 8.0). Each MAO_{Tb} variant was eluted using 5 mL elution buffer (50 mM TRIS-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, 500 mM imidazole, pH 8.0). Using a PD10 buffer exchange column (Cytiva) the elution buffer was exchanged with the storage buffer 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer pH 7.5. For crystallization experiments, the protein purity was further purified by gel filtration using HiLoad Superdex 200 16/60 column (Cytiva), equilibrated with 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer pH 7.5 using an ÄKTA pure™ system (Cytiva). Activity assays on MAO_{Tb} were carried out by the horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-coupled assay in 50 mM HEPES/NaOH buffer pH 7.5, following published protocols [13]. The assay mixture comprised 0.10 mM 4-aminoantipyrine, 1.0 mM 3,5-dichloro-2-hydroxybenzenesulfonate and 0.013 mg mL⁻¹ HRP. Initial assays were carried out to screen different amines as substrates at a final concentration of 4 mM (Table 1). The reaction was started by adding 1.0 µM enzyme except for *n*-hexylamine (10 nM enzyme) and *n*-heptylamine (3.0 nM enzyme) in order to avoid signal overflow on the most active substrates. The absorbance changes were monitored at 515 nm ($\epsilon_{515} = 26 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) using a Cary 100 UV-visible spectrophotometer (Agilent) at 25 °C. The same HRP-coupled assay was used to measure and calculate the steady-state parameters for all MAO_{Tb} variants. Measurements were performed in 50 mM HEPES/NaOH buffer pH 7.5, using between 0.10 and 1.0 µM enzyme, depending on the substrate, while varying the substrate concentration between 0.10 and 10 mM. Data were fitted into a Michaelis-Menten equation using GraphPad Prism 8.0 software (La Jolla, CA, USA).

2.3. Protein crystallization and structure elucidation

Crystals of the wild-type MAO_{Tb} were obtained as previously reported [12]. Briefly, the sitting drop vapor diffusion technique was used by mixing equal volumes of the protein sample (6.5 mg mL⁻¹ in 50 mM potassium phosphate pH 7.5) and the reservoir solution (22%–30 %

Table 1

Substrate screening of MAO_{Tb} variants based on HRP-coupled assay at a fixed concentration of substrates of 4.0 mM. The measurements, in duplicates, were performed in 50 mM HEPES/NaOH buffer pH 7.5.

compound	k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)				
	WT	A168D	A168R	T199W	V324W
benzylamine	0.04 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.0003	0.1 ± 0.007	0.015 ± 0.003
	0.04 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.002	0.03 ± 0.0008	0.3 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.01
kynuramine	0	0	0.01 ± 0.0006	0.06 ± 0.001	0.04 ± 0.004
	0.03 ± 0.01	0.2 ± 0.02	0.01 ± 0.0004	0.04 ± 0.008	0.07 ± 0.002
phenyl-ethyl-amine	0.1 ± 0.02	2.1 ± 0.1	0.03 ± 0.002	0.2 ± 0.002	0.39 ± 0.13
	0.02	0.1	0.002	0.002	0.13
putrescine	0	2.3 ± 0.3	0.05 ± 0.002	0.3 ± 0.0001	0.70 ± 0.13
	0	0	0	0	0
spermidine	0	0	0	0	0
	0.5 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.04	0.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.03
spermine	1.2 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.04	4.7 ± 0.1	19.8 ± 0.4	14.47 ± 1.6
	14.1 ± 1.9	3.4 ± 0.02	27.3 ± 2.7	65.3 ± 5.4	67.22 ± 4.6
cyclobutylamine	4.2 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.5	25.4 ± 1.5	22.18 ± 1.4
	0.4	0.2	0.5	1.5	1.4
cyclohexylamine	64.4 ± 0.9	8.2 ± 0.9	30.4 ± 1.0	114.5 ± 7.8	197.03 ± 6.7
	0.5 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.04	0.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.03
<i>n</i> -butylamine	1.2 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.04	4.7 ± 0.1	19.8 ± 0.4	14.47 ± 1.6
	14.1 ± 1.9	3.4 ± 0.02	27.3 ± 2.7	65.3 ± 5.4	67.22 ± 4.6
<i>n</i> -pentylamine	4.2 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.5	25.4 ± 1.5	22.18 ± 1.4
	0.4	0.2	0.5	1.5	1.4
<i>n</i> -hexylamine	64.4 ± 0.9	8.2 ± 0.9	30.4 ± 1.0	114.5 ± 7.8	197.03 ± 6.7
	0.5 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.04	0.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.03
<i>n</i> -heptylamine	1.2 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.04	4.7 ± 0.1	19.8 ± 0.4	14.47 ± 1.6
	14.1 ± 1.9	3.4 ± 0.02	27.3 ± 2.7	65.3 ± 5.4	67.22 ± 4.6
methyl	4.2 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.5	25.4 ± 1.5	22.18 ± 1.4
	0.4	0.2	0.5	1.5	1.4
hexylamine	64.4 ± 0.9	8.2 ± 0.9	30.4 ± 1.0	114.5 ± 7.8	197.03 ± 6.7
	0.5 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.04	0.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.03
<i>n</i> -heptylamine	1.2 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.04	4.7 ± 0.1	19.8 ± 0.4	14.47 ± 1.6
	14.1 ± 1.9	3.4 ± 0.02	27.3 ± 2.7	65.3 ± 5.4	67.22 ± 4.6

PEG4000, 100 mM TRIS/HCl buffer pH 8.5, 200 mM MgCl₂) obtaining yellow spear-shaped crystals after 7–10 days at 20 °C. X-ray diffraction data were collected at the beamtime ID30A-3 for putrescine and spermidine, ID23-2 for benzylamine, and ID30A-1 for *n*-heptylamine (ESRF, Grenoble, France). Soaking experiments were performed by embedding the crystals into the reservoir solution containing 1–10 mM of substrates till bleaching of the crystals was observed. For data collection, crystals were transferred into a mother liquor solution containing 20 % (v/v) glycerol and 1–10 mM of the substrate, followed by flash-cooling in a stream of gaseous nitrogen at 100 K. Data processing and scaling were carried out using XDS [14] and programs of the CCP4 package [15]. The coordinates of wild-type MAO_{Tb} in the unbound form (PDB code: 8P84) were used after removal of all water molecules for molecular replacement using MolRep from the CCP4 package [15]. Model building and structure analysis were performed by the program COOT [16], whereas refinement was performed by REFMAC5 [17]. Non-crystallographic symmetry (NCS) restraints were strictly applied during the initial refinement steps of the refinement process. Data collection and refinement statistics are presented in [Supplementary Table 1](#). Figures were created by ChimeraX [18]. Atomic coordinates and structure factors were deposited with the Protein Data Bank (PDB codes: 9H5Z for the MAO_{Tb}-benzylamine complex, 9H5Q for the MAO_{Tb}-spermidine complex, 9H5P for the MAO_{Tb}-putrescine complex, 9H64 for the MAO_{Tb}-*n*-heptylamine complex).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Crystal structures of MAO_{Tb} in complex with substrates

The rational engineering of enzymes is primarily based on structure-function relationship analysis and multiple sequence alignment approaches [19]. MAOs are a family of FAD-dependent enzymes sharing common structural features at the core of the active site which are conserved from bacteria to humans, such as the aromatic cage in front of the flavin cofactor (*re* face) and a Lys residue H-bonded to the FAD N5 atom through a water molecule supposed to represent the oxygen binding pocket [20]. This region of the active site is crucial for properly orienting the C–N bond with respect to the flavin ring to ensure efficient catalysis. Adjacent to this core region is an area extending to the protein surface that is characterized by variability in size and shape, reflecting substrate specificity of different amine oxidases. Compared with other FAD-dependent amine oxidases, MAO_{Tb} features a wider cavity that does not appear to be specifically tailored to linear aliphatic monoamines [12]. Moreover, no acidic residues, which may foster amine binding, are present within the cavity and patches of negative electrostatic potential are observed only on the protein surface. To understand the mechanism of MAO_{Tb} substrate binding and to identify active site residues for site-directed mutagenesis, we determined the crystal structure of the enzyme in complex with substrates. In general, *in crystallo* enzyme turnover may hamper the possibility to get a stable complex with substrates, but MAO_{Tb} crystals have a very low solvent content (45 %) and a limited molecular diffusion may help in slowing down oxygen diffusion, substrate binding and product release. Hence, we proceeded by soaking wild-type MAO_{Tb} crystals in the crystallization solution using 1–10 mM of substrate for a few seconds followed by flash-freezing in liquid nitrogen. Crystals were clearly bleached, which demonstrated that the reaction occurred. A number of crystals were tested because some of them broke during the treatment and others did not lead to an interpretable electron density map. Crystal structures of MAO_{Tb} in complex with putrescine (at 2.3 Å resolution), benzylamine (at 2.2 Å resolution), *n*-heptylamine (at 1.6 Å resolution) and spermidine (at 1.8 Å resolution) were obtained by molecular replacement using the native crystal structure (PDB code 8P84) deprived of water molecules as a model. In all cases, the dimeric organization observed for the native enzyme was found, with rmsd between the C_α pairs in the 0.1–0.4 Å range.

The MAO_{Tb} structure in complex with putrescine at 2.3 Å resolution remarkably revealed two substrate molecules bound to protomer A of the enzyme dimer, while a unique putrescine unit was assigned to protomer B. This variability is probably due to the dynamic interaction of the enzyme with this linear and relatively small diamine substrate. In protomer A, one putrescine molecule binds in front of the flavin, whereas the other is located more distant from the active site ([Fig. 1a](#)). Instead, in protomer B the unique putrescine molecule occupies the same position as the second one in protomer A, i.e. more distant from the flavin ring (not shown). In protomer A the putrescine molecule occupying the cavity area in front of FAD is stabilized by three H-bonds formed by one of the two amine groups with the hydroxyl group of Tyr188 and Tyr432 and with the carbonyl group of Val172 ([Fig. 1a](#)). The second amine group is in an optimal position to be oxidized, with a distance of 3.30 Å between the carbon of the putrescine and the N5 of the FAD. Putrescine is a poor substrate for MAO_{Tb} (k_{obs} 0.03 s⁻¹ at 4.0 mM putrescine; [Table 1](#)) and this can be explained by the fact that the network of H-bonds formed by the first amine hampers product release and enzyme turnover.

The MAO_{Tb} structure in complex with benzylamine was determined at 2.2 Å resolution and in protomer B the electron density clearly showed the aromatic ring and the amine group bound in the aromatic cage formed by the Tyr395-Tyr432 pair ([Fig. 1b](#)), whereas nothing is bound in protomer A. Also benzylamine is a poor substrate for MAO_{Tb} (k_{obs} 0.04 s⁻¹ at 4.0 mM benzylamine; [Table 1](#)), which may be due to the position of the C–N bond which is not ideal for the oxidative attack by the flavin. As mentioned above, the active site cavity of MAO_{Tb} is wider and also the area adjacent to the catalytic core includes residues Ala168, Thr199 and Val324 ([Fig. 1](#)) which in human MAOs correspond to bulkier amino acids (Phe, Phe/Ile and Ile/Tyr, respectively). In particular, Phe208/Ile199 and Ile335/Tyr326 in human MAO A/B regulate ligand binding by functioning as gating residues [21]. This suggests that in MAO_{Tb} this “door” is always open because residues Thr199 and Val324 have a smaller side chain with a more limited conformational modulation. It cannot be ruled out that in *Thermoanaerobacteriales* bacterium, as well as in other bacteria, MAO_{Tb} substrates may not be limited to small linear aliphatic monoamines. The enzyme may be prone to bind a broad range of exogenous amines functioning either as a scavenger to protect against hazardous molecules or as a hunter of amines as a source of nitrogen.

Soaking experiments of MAO_{Tb} with spermidine resulted in a structure at 1.8 Å and inspection of the active site clearly revealed a different electron density map in the two protomers of the dimeric protein. In protomer A, two elongated densities were found which could be fitted with the products deriving from spermidine oxidation, i.e. 1,3-diaminopropane and 4-aminobutanal ([Fig. 1c](#)). The former is bound in front of FAD with one amine group stabilized by an H-bond to a water molecule near Tyr188 and the second amine group at 3.3 Å distance from the N5 of the FAD. The aldehyde product is instead located in the back of the active site with respect to FAD, in a similar position as the second putrescine molecule ([Figs. 1a and 2](#)). Ambiguity may exist because the electron density could be fitted with 4-aminobutanal modelled in the opposite way, i.e. with the amino group towards 1,3-diaminopropane and the aldehyde group in the back of the active site. Nevertheless, this is unlikely because the aldehyde group derives from the breakdown of spermidine into 1,3-diaminopropane and 4-aminobutanal and, moreover, the electron density is more compatible with a C=O bond (rather than a longer C–N bond). Spermidine is indeed a substrate of MAO_{Tb} though at low rate (k_{obs} 0.1 s⁻¹ at 4.0 mM spermidine, [Table 1](#)) and these results indicate that MAO_{Tb} can also act on secondary amines, which was suggested also by the activity on methyl-hexylamine [12] ([Table 1](#)). Interestingly, in protomer B a more extended electron density peak was interpreted as the intact spermidine molecule, which was captured in a position corresponding to the substrate approaching the active site ([Supplementary Fig. 1](#)). This is in agreement with the situation observed for putrescine and can be once again attributed to the wide

Fig. 1. Zoomed view of MAO_{Tb} active sites architectures as observed from crystals soaked with putrescine (a), benzylamine (b), spermidine (c), *n*-heptylamine (d). Refined 2Fo-Fc electron-density contoured at 1.5 σ is shown as gray chicken-wire representation. The FAD cofactor is shown with carbon atoms in yellow. MAO_{Tb} residues are represented with carbon, oxygen, and nitrogen, atoms in cornflower blue, red, and blue respectively. Water molecules are drawn as red spheres. For the sake of clarity, only residues decorating the part of the cavity occupied by the ligands are shown. Carbon atoms of putrescine, benzylamine and heptylamine are shown in orange, purple and salmon, respectively, whereas nitrogen atoms are in blue. Products of spermidine oxidation in panel (c) are drawn as follows: carbon atoms of 1,3-diaminopropane and 4-aminobutanal are in green and light sea green, respectively. Oxygen and nitrogen atoms are in red and blue, respectively. Dashed lines indicate hydrogen bonds. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

and open cavity of MAO_{Tb}.

The crystal structure of the MAO_{Tb} in complex with *n*-heptylamine was solved at 1.6 Å resolution (Fig. 1d). An elongated electron density map in both protomers was observed which could be fitted with the aliphatic monoamine substrate. In this case, ambiguity may arise relatively to the position of the amine group. However, when modelled in this way the amine group is stabilized by hydrogen bonds with conserved water molecules, whereas the opposite conformation is unlikely because it would not be in the proper orientation to be oxidized by

the flavin.

Superposition of the MAO_{Tb} crystal structures in complex with the four substrates revealed that, as mentioned above, the rmsd between the C α pairs is within the 0.1–0.4 Å and that the architecture of the active site is conserved, except for few loops at the entrance of the active site cavity that undergo minimal movements (not shown). This indicates that substrate binding does not cause any significant conformational change. This comparative analysis allowed to highlight a channel that the linear ligands follow to reach the catalytic site in front of the flavin

Fig. 2. Superposition of the crystal structures of MAO_{Tb} bound to the four substrates described in Fig. 1. As a reference, FAD and the Tyr395 and Tyr432 pair forming the aromatic cage with the flavin are shown. Color code is as in Fig. 1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

(Fig. 2). Although some space is available at the bottom of the aromatic cage, substrates do not venture further into the cavity and extend just enough towards FAD to be properly oriented for oxidation to occur. The benzylamine ring overlaps with the plane traced by the central part of *n*-heptylamine. In human MAOs, aromatic ligands bind coplanar with the Tyr-Tyr pair and this observation may suggest that in MAO_{Tb} the architecture of the active site hampers this conformation, which may represent another reason why benzylamine is a poor substrate.

3.2. Analysis of MAO_{Tb} variants

Based on the comparison of MAO_{Tb} active site architecture to that of

human MAOs and on the analysis of the enzyme structures in complex with substrates, we identified residues Ala168, Thr199 and Val324 as hotspots for site-directed mutagenesis. The objectives were (i) exploring the role of non-conserved residues of the active site, (ii) improving enzyme activity on aliphatic amines, (iii) broadening substrate specificity towards aromatic ligands. Although Ala168 corresponds to Phe in human MAOs, the introduction of either a positively (A168R) or negatively-charged (A168D) side chain was meant to probe the effect on amine binding. In addition, replacing Thr199 and Val324 with bulkier amino acids was aimed at restricting the area of the active site adjacent to the catalytic core to avoid unproductive binding of substrate molecules. Moreover, the idea to introduce an aromatic residue was adopted to improve the MAO_{Tb} activity on aromatic amines. In humans (and similarly in other mammals) a Phe-Ile (MAO A) and an Ile-Tyr (MAO B) pair at this site creates a combination of gating residues that finely tune the shape of the cavity and the different ligand binding specificity. The idea was to replace a single residue (either on the 199 site or on residue 324) endowed with a side chain whose conformation may effectively create a barrier that can be nevertheless negotiated by substrates to get access to the catalytic site. A Trp residue was chosen and two MAO_{Tb} variants T199W and V324W were designed. By using a Quik-Change methodology, the vectors containing the mutated MAO_{Tb} cDNAs were transformed into *E. coli* NEB10 β and purified as His-tagged recombinant proteins. All variants showed purification profiles similar to the wild-type protein. Thermal shift assays demonstrated that all proteins retain the same stability as the wild-type MAO_{Tb} (data not shown).

To test the substrate specificity of MAO_{Tb} variants, activity assays using the HRP-coupled protocol were performed at 4.0 mM substrate concentrations, as done with the wild-type enzyme [12] (Table 1). Substrate screening showed that all variants are inactive on cyclobutylamine and cyclohexylamine, just as the wild-type enzyme. A168R MAO_{Tb} is equally or less active on all substrates; a minimal improvement was observed with phenylethylamine and spermine. Instead, A168D was one order of magnitude more active with putrescine and showed a significant improvement in activity for spermidine and spermine. Activity on *n*-hexylamine and *n*-heptylamine was lower. This clearly indicates that the introduction of a negatively charged group at the entrance of the catalytic site can significantly improve the binding of polyamines but has a detrimental effect on the activity towards aliphatic monoamines, in agreement with the crystal structures showing the alkyl chain extending to the back the catalytic site. The T199W replacement led to an increase in the activity on benzylamine and kynuramine (and also on phenylethylamine to a lower extent) and is significantly more active on aliphatic monoamines. This confirms the preference of MAO_{Tb} for aliphatic rather than aromatic amines but suggests that this site of the active site may be promising for further improvements. Replacement of V324 to Trp had a similar effect relatively to kynuramine and aliphatic amines, whereas the activity with benzylamine was lower. Interestingly, a better improvement with respect to wild-type and to T199W was found with polyamines.

On the basis of substrate screening (Table 1), the variant/substrate combinations that showed an increase in k_{obs} of at least 5-fold with respect to wild-type were selected for a complete kinetic characterization to determine the steady-state kinetic parameters (Table 2). The A168D variant showed an 8-fold increase in k_{cat} and a mild decrease in K_M with putrescine which results in almost a 10-fold improvement in k_{cat}/K_M . Instead, A168D was more active than wild-type enzyme on spermine and spermidine (Table 1) but we observed a linear increase of k_{obs} as a function of substrate concentration which could not be fitted into a Michaelis-Menten equation (data not shown). Steady-state kinetic parameters of A168D were determined also for *n*-hexylamine as this molecule represents the benchmark substrate for MAO_{Tb}. Indeed, in agreement with the initial screening, no significant improvement was obtained. The T199W variant is more active on aromatic monoamines, with a k_{cat}/K_M value for benzylamine which is one order of magnitude higher than the wild-type enzyme and a similar situation was registered

Table 2

Steady-state kinetic parameters of MAO_{Tb} variants with substrates selected from the screening (Table 1). The measurements, in duplicates, were performed at 25 °C in 50 mM HEPES/NaOH buffer pH 7.5 by using the HRP-coupled assay at varied substrate concentrations. Values are expressed in s⁻¹ for k_{cat} , mM for K_M and s⁻¹mM⁻¹ for k_{cat}/K_M , respectively.

substrate	wild-type			A168D			T199W			V324W		
	k_{cat}	K_M	k_{cat}/K_M	k_{cat}	K_M	k_{cat}/K_M	k_{cat}	K_M	k_{cat}/K_M	k_{cat}	K_M	k_{cat}/K_M
benzylamine	0.047 ± 0.004	0.83 ± 0.21	0.06	not determined ^b			0.12 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.03	0.60	not determined ^b		
kynuramine	no saturation ^a			not determined ^b			0.38 ± 0.01	1.6 ± 0.1	0.24	0.19 ± 0.01	0.75 ± 0.10	0.25
putrescine	0.11 ± 0.01	6.4 ± 1.5	0.02	0.81 ± 0.03	4.5 ± 0.4	0.18	not determined ^b			not determined ^b		
n-pentylamine	13.3 ± 3.3	42.9 ± 15.9	0.31	not determined ^b			153 ± 8	1.4 ± 0.3	109	53.2 ± 1.3	5.0 ± 0.30	10.6
n-hexylamine	44.0 ± 2.0	4.3 ± 0.7	10.2	27.3 ± 1.2	1.4 ± 0.3	19.5	268 ± 10	0.13 ± 0.02	2060	138 ± 4.4	0.60 ± 0.08	229
methyl hexylamine	13.2 ± 1.3	7.1 ± 1.5	1.9	not determined ^b			224 ± 6.4	0.53 ± 0.07	420	60.8 ± 5.2	1.10 ± 0.34	55.3
n-heptylamine	69.8 ± 3.3	0.80± 0.15	87	not determined ^b			135 ± 4.8	0.05 ± 0.01	2700	211 ± 126	0.22 ± 0.04	960

^a Linear increase of k_{obs} as a function of substrate concentration (above 10 mM).

^b Not determined: no improvement in the initial screening with respect to wild-type enzyme was observed (Table 1).

with kynuramine, whose steady-state parameters could not even be determined for the wild-type enzyme. A remarkable increase in activity was found with all aliphatic monoamines, with increases in k_{cat}/K_M values of more than 200-fold for pentylamine, hexylamine, methyl-hexylamine and more than 30-fold for heptylamine (Table 2). This results not only from an increase in the oxidation rate but also from a significant decrease in K_M values, indicating that the introduction of a Trp gate contributes to preventing unproductive binding of substrates. When the same residue is used to replace Val324, a clear though less pronounced effect with respect to T199W was found. The activity of V324W is improved on kynuramine similarly to T199W, whereas parameters on benzylamine were not determined because no improvement was registered during the initial screening. Similarly to A168D, despite a higher activity with spermine and spermidine in the initial screening (Table 1), increasing values of k_{obs} were observed for V324W, which nevertheless could not be fitted into a Michaelis-Menten equation (data not shown). The k_{cat}/K_M values of V324W for aliphatic monoamines were 10-fold–34-fold higher than those of the wild-type enzyme (Table 2), an improvement that is one order of magnitude less pronounced than that observed for T199W. This might be due either to a more limited “gating effect” of the Trp side chain at position 324 with respect to position 199, or, conversely, to a lower conformational flexibility of the former which may improve unproductive substrate binding but also prevent product release.

4. Conclusion

MAO enzymes have acquired a considerable interest over the years, not only as human drug targets but also as biocatalysts because amine oxidation is a relevant reaction in many industrial applications [22]. In this context, microbial MAOs are of interest because homologous enzymes of higher eukaryotes are membrane proteins and therefore

difficult to manipulate. MAO_{Tb} is a thermostable enzyme from *Thermoanaerobacteriales* bacterium which can be produced at high yield as recombinant and soluble protein in *E. coli* [12]. We previously demonstrated that MAO_{Tb} is highly active on *n*-alkyl amines such as *n*-hexylamine and *n*-heptylamine. In this study the crystal structures of MAO_{Tb} in complex with various substrates, including putrescine, benzylamine, spermidine, and *n*-heptylamine, were determined to get insights into substrate-binding mechanisms of the enzyme and to guide site-directed mutagenesis experiments. Substrate specificity and catalytic efficiency are influenced by the ability of ligands to be stabilized within the active site, particularly in the case of polyamines like putrescine and spermidine whose multiple amine groups are known to form hydrogen bonds or electrostatic interactions. Moreover, Thr199 and Val324 were also explored as target sites for site-directed mutagenesis because the corresponding residues in other MAOs function as gating residues to access the catalytic core area. Indeed, mutagenesis of key residues Ala168, Thr199 and Val324 demonstrated significant changes in substrate specificity and activity. The A168D variant showed an improvement in the activity on putrescine, but the mild effect indicates that MAO_{Tb} is indeed an oxidase acting on substrates bearing one amine group. T199W and V324W variants showed a slightly higher activity on aromatic amines and a marked enhancement on aliphatic amines. In particular, T199W is one order of magnitude better with benzylamine and showed k_{cat}/K_M values on *n*-alkyl-monoamines up to 350-fold higher than those of the wild-type enzyme. Overall, these results underscore the importance of structural features in dictating substrate preference of MAO_{Tb} and prove that the enzyme is prone to manipulate and engineer.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lorenzo Basile: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis,

Data curation, Conceptualization. **Chiara Poli:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lars L. Santema:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Răzvan C. Lesenciuc:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Marco W. Fraaije:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Claudia Binda:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Data availability statement

The data will be available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abb.2024.110276>.

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